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ETHICS IS A DISEMPOWERED SUBJECT IN THE ENGINEERING CURRICULUM

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ABSTRACT

Power, as enacted in educational practices, is a critical issue that shapes all aspects of engineering education. Yet, there is little research within engineering education on how power manifests itself in what we teach and how we teach it. In this paper we use engineering ethics education as an exemplar to interrogate how power tacitly influences the practice of engineering ethics education. To infer the status of engineering ethics as an academic subject we examine, theorize, and elaborate on two aspects of power: (1) the internal power relations affecting the education of engineering ethics and how they manifest within engineering institutions, and (2) the exerting power of key external actors in and ways in which they impact engineering ethics education. Our methodological approach relies on autoethnographic data rooted in the perspective of the three authors. The autoethnographic cases are grounded in the authors' own teaching and research practices in engineering ethics education set in the US, Irish and Dutch context. We perform a cross-comparative analysis to reflect further on the impact of power relations on ethics as an academic subject and make recommendations for engineering ethics education research and practice.

1. INTRODUCTION

Power is a concept with a long history in philosophy and in the 20th century made its way also as a core concept for the social sciences. According to Bertrand Russell [1], power is as fundamental for social sciences as energy is for physics. With its long history come several theoretical articulations of the concept, and while it is outside the scope of the paper to posit one understanding of power as correct, we do want to raise awareness of the importance of this concept when considering the intersection between engineering practice and education.

1.1. Theorising power

Theories of power can be categorized as “micro-centric” in their focus on the actual or potential actions of individuals and groups, or “macro-centric” in their focus on the

structural context that constrains, enables or shapes individuals. A pluralist stance does not see these different understandings as incompatible, but as providing different analytical lenses (Table 1, inspired by Allen [2] and Sattarov [3]). As such, it acknowledges both the capacity of individuals to make a difference, but also considers how they might be externally determined in their actions, dispositions or beliefs.

Table 1. *Theoretical conceptions of power*

Level	Type	Example
Micro	Dispositional	Power as the property of individual actors to bring about their desired outcome -- "X is able to"
Micro	Episodic	Power as the property of the relation between two or more individual or collective actors -- "X has influence over Y and Z"
Macro	Systemic	Power as structural pressure -- "X is constrained to act this way in her social community"
Macro	Constitutive	Power as a constitutive dimension -- "X is shaped in her social relations by external factors"

1.2. Power in engineering practice

Engineering practice has been described as political [4], inasmuch as it is embedded in power contexts [5], constitutive of power relations [6], shaped by power differentials [7], and a contributor to the distribution of power in society ([8]; [9]).

Nevertheless, we also encounter an epistemic myopia and lack of self-reflectiveness, with Little *et al* [10] signalling that it is "unlikely" that practicing engineers understand the political nature of their work, as well as an absence of discussions of power relations within organisations and how they affect the ends to which engineering is put [11]. More so, it has been argued that this conformity to the employer's interests and lack of reflective resistance is built into the education of engineers [12].

1.3. Power in education practice

Not only is power essential to engineering practice, it is also enacted in educational practices and shapes all aspects of engineering education. Formal education is one of the central ways in which power and hierarchy are organized in society [13]. Learners learn early how to recognize and perform power, including the negative effects of it, like bias and marginalization [14]. Beyond the micro-context of classroom interactions where power is evident, there is also the macro-context of education and schooling where political power is embedded. Power struggles are encountered over the purpose of education, as well as about the selection and transformation of knowledge into curriculum, and its enactment in the classroom through teaching and assessment ([15], [16]).

1.4. Ethics as an exemplar for exploring power in engineering education

Despite the importance of power in both education and engineering practices, there is little research within engineering education on how power manifests itself to shape what and how we teach. The concept of power has been addressed in higher education studies to a lesser extent than in other disciplines of fundamental social interest [17]. More so, while educators can identify the manifestation of power in practice, this is mostly divorced from theorizing its mechanisms [18], or its epistemic

dimension [19]. The concept of power thus appears to be either ignored or under-theorised in higher education research [20].

In this paper, we use engineering ethics education (EEE) as an exemplar to interrogate the issue of power within engineering education. Even when it is not made explicit, power tacitly shapes the EEE practice. Our contribution aims to explore how power is manifest and impacts EEE. To infer the status of engineering ethics as an academic subject we examine, theorize, and elaborate on two aspects of power: (1) the internal power relations affecting the education of engineering ethics and how they manifest within engineering institutions, and (2) the exerting power of key external actors in and ways in which they impact engineering ethics education.

2. METHODOLOGY

To address these questions, we pursue an autoethnographical research approach that brings forward the authors' experiences, recounted against a model of the major influences impacting the higher education curriculum.

2.1. A sensemaking model of power relations in engineering ethics education

For the purpose of tracing the influences impacting EEE and situating our own experiences researching and teaching engineering ethics, we adopted the academic plan model developed by Lattuca and Stark [21]. The model (fig 1) is based on extensive literature review of the intended curriculum in higher education and puts forward a set of clearly defined and inter-related concepts operational at different levels. These are represented by the components of the curriculum itself (i.e. purpose, content, sequence, learners, instructional resources, instructional processes, assessment and evaluation), unit-level influences (i.e. faculty members, characteristics of the discipline, student characteristics), institutional influences (e.g. college mission, resources, governance) and external influences (i.e. market forces, government, accrediting agencies, disciplinary associations).

Fig 1. The academic plan in sociocultural context (Lattuca & Stark [21], p.5)

This model allows us to address some of the limitations of higher education research which tends to focus either on individual actors such as instructors or on the levels of institutions, policy and society as independent from each other ([22]; [23]; [24]). The model by Lattuca and Stark [21] also serves a pluralist understanding of power, by acknowledging different levels and manifestations of influence. It also views individual

actors, such as engineering ethics instructors, as affected by forces external or internal to their academic environment, but also reacting to them and influencing the academic plan.

2.2. An autoethnographical approach to power in engineering ethics education

To render how these diverse influences play out in EEE, we use autoethnography. Autoethnography is an autobiographical ethnographic method of qualitative research. It is used to recount the researchers' personal experiences, that are then subjected to an analysis of the sociocultural context and of their implications ([25], [26]). The method has a descriptive component, inasmuch as it is "a means of telling one's story", and an analytical component, given the deep introspection involved and the attempts of reporting these experiences in a systematic manner [27]. Its strength lies in the insider perspective into a matter of significance, which might evade other research approaches in which the researcher's stance is more that of an "outsider looking in." The criticality that accompanies recounting is crucial for autoethnography [28]. Through its critical outlook, autoethnographic research can pose a challenge to entrenched beliefs and practices, linking story with theory to the point of merging [29].

The autoethnographic process behind this contribution unfolded between autumn 2020-spring 2021 over several stages:

Preliminary stage: spontaneous, unprompted reflection on how the topic of power is manifested in the authors' EEE practice. The dialogue led to the identification of power in EEE as a topic of concern;

Stage 1: recounting and documenting personal experiences related to the topic;

Stage 2: discussing theoretical understandings of the topic, and agreeing on a sensemaking model to frame the authors' experiences with teaching and researching engineering ethics (see Fig 1);

Stage 3: connecting theory and story, by articulating personal experiences with teaching and researching engineering ethics inspired by the sensemaking model.

3. RESULTS

To report the results of the fourth stage of the autoethnographic research process, we followed Adams *et al.*'s ([29], p.94) advice for connecting story and theory. Theory offers the foundation that guides the recounting of one's experiences and supports the elaboration in a critical manner of their meanings and implications. We incorporate this advice by mapping our experiences against the model presented in Fig 1.

3.1. Power in engineering ethics education in the Irish context

Statement of positionality: Author1 has examined for her doctoral study the implementation, teaching and accreditation of ethics in 6 institutions in Ireland. She also co-taught for 4 years with a social scientist in an Irish College of Engineering a course of professional formation for 1st year students.

The system of engineering education in Ireland is marked by a distinction in prestige between universities and institutes of technology [30]. It is also subject to accreditation by Engineers Ireland, which is an original signatory of the Washington Accord. Engineers Ireland has the double function of an accrediting body mandating the outcomes that engineering programmes across the country must meet, and a professional body representing the profession.

Prestige appeared to play a part in how the institutions offering the title of Chartered Engineer relate to the accrediting body and adapt their curricula to their

recommendations. As a newer outcome, ethics started to make its way in the curriculum through the push of Engineers Ireland [31]. The increased presence of ethics following the introduction of a dedicated criterion more than a decade ago has been described as a move “from zero,” from “virtually nothing on ethics.” In my study [32], I “stumbled upon” the fact that the participant institutes of technology appear to have more courses with a contribution to the dedicated ethics outcome than university programmes do, especially high-ranking ones. Is then the focus on ethics in the engineering curriculum an instantiation of *power over*, and the lesser focus an act of resistance by actors who themselves are considered powerful in virtue of a long tradition of alumni, research and university rankings?

How many layers of *power over* can we identify? Indeed, the accrediting body influences the engineering curriculum, at minimum by having a set of broad outcomes that programmes have to meet. At the same time, every accreditation event includes an Employers’ session, the programme submission includes the Employers’ view, and the feedback of Employers is incorporated in recommendations -- recommendations that engineering programmes need to take on board or provide a strong justification for why they had not done so. Analysing accreditation reports and observing accreditation events for my doctoral study, some recurring recommendations were to “strengthen ties with industry” or “introducing employers in the advisory board”. Such recommendations were mentioned in connection with several outcomes, including ethics.

If ethics is an academic subject constituted through a power process, and an outcome of a *power over*, how does it relate to power actors, such as the big corporations set in Dublin which could very well be the Employer of future graduates? Are students taught in a way that serves these actors, or are they also taught to resist them?

What about the instructors teaching a subject that made its way in the curriculum in an unnatural manner, at the intervention of a powerful actor, rather than as an outcome of the beliefs of the faculty body and the programme leadership about what constitutes “good” engineering practice and education? In my study, I encountered instructors for whom the issue of empowerment mattered, as they described “fighting” a decades old battle for having ethics in the curriculum. Having a dedicated accreditation criterion helped them make the case to department leaders for the introduction of ethics in the curriculum. At the same time, the question of empowering ethics as an academic subject also matters, inasmuch as several of the instructors teaching dedicated ethics courses did not opt or did not want to teach ethics, and declare that were they in their students’ shoes, they would not even attend their sessions. What does it then mean to empower an academic subject and through what means?

3.2. Power in engineering ethics education in the Dutch context

Statement of positionality: Author2 is coordinator of a 20 ECTS program in a Dutch technological university. The program aims to raise engineering students’ awareness on users, society and entrepreneurship aspects of technological innovation.

Eindhoven University of Technology started in 2012 a 20 ECTS program on User, Society and Enterprise to raise awareness on these aspects of technological innovation. Back then, these credits shifted from the departments to the general level. EEE in the Netherlands is quite autonomous from accreditation bodies and disciplinary associations. Ethics teachers are not directed towards teaching or controlled to teach a particular vision or topic. From the personal perspective of the second author, we

formulate the hypothesis that the resistance to the USE program might have epistemic, university-department and ecosystem power dynamic origins.

First, based on empirical evidence gained during discussions, we can state that, epistemically, many engineering faculty see less the relevance of these ethics and social sciences courses than they see the relevance of their “own” courses. Underlying is probably a more fundamental discussion between two epistemic views. On the one hand, a rational epistemic view considers that facts and engineering experts should be leading in societal discussions. On the other hand, a more discursive view that science and engineering knowledge and experts are one source in a societal decision making process with its particular strengths and weaknesses, next to other sources like democracy, politics, finances, marketing, law, or communication (Jasanoff, 1998).

We hypothesise that this tension is strengthened by a university-department power dynamic. In the financial approach of education of a university, 20 ECTS for the yearly 2000 students is a substantial financial amount. Because of the Dutch and the organisational translations of the higher education financial mechanisms, it therefore is understandable that the EEE discussions become linked with the financial ones.

As a third aspect of influence in this debate, it might be interesting to gain more insights in the role of industry in the ecosystem of the university. Times Higher Education, which ranked universities in terms of their relationships with innovative technology companies (known as Global Innovators), and the amount of scientific papers produced in such collaborations, puts TU/e at the top of this list. As a positive consequence, the close collaboration raises extra funding. It also inserts a tension of scientific independence and autonomy as companies might expect return on investment and might be able to increase their impact on the university as an organisation.

3.3. Power in engineering ethics education in the US context

Author 3: has taught the required ethics course in their program for 5 years and also done curriculum development for the course. They also undertake funded research on EEE.

At its core, in the engineering curriculum in the U.S., ethics is taught largely to fulfil accreditation requirements. Therefore, agencies that accredit degree programs have significant power over what the curricula should include and if it should have ethics. Beyond that there are also power issues and compromises within a local level unit, program or department, about how much space should be given to ethics, in particular, if there should be a standalone course for ethics instruction or if it should be part of other courses. There are negotiations that take place around it and concessions made. The other issue here is who is going to teach, and in my experience nobody really wants to or those who want to only do so for the reason that it might be an easier course to teach (e.g., go through some slides and assign some readings). The biggest power issue is that ethics is not empowered, it is neutral and not even considered something to focus on. This lack of agency and power reflects the space ethics occupies.

It is common to hear that “ethics is very important” as a refrain but not when it comes to making space for it within the curriculum. Why is that? One, it is disempowered because it is not a technical subject and not considered core to the discipline. Second, it is an interdisciplinary topic that does not have easily demarcated boundaries around it and therefore it is harder, compared to a technical subject, to design a syllabus. Third, it projects a certain image of the instructor and within the larger technical enterprise that image is marginalized -- someone who teaches non-technical topics.

Fourth, it brings up uncomfortable discussions with no easy or clear-cut answers that are hard for faculty who are not trained in the topic to lead. Overall, the disempowering situation of lack of recognition within the department; image of a course that someone *must* teach, and lack of resources also makes the course more neutral rather than critical.

From the student perspective, it is a topic which when taught well they find empowering. They are able to discuss topics that they find important, especially once they read about it, and which they are unable to discuss in any other space. In other words, a well taught ethics course puts pressure on other aspects of curriculum and course of study as well. The topics and use of cases from the industry also allow students to make a direct link between what is taught and workplace practices and although this might not lead directly to a job, it does lead to awareness from when students face these issues on the job.

4. CONCLUSION

We present autoethnography as *parrhesia*, a notion of truth speaking as speaking openly about one's own situation and making oneself vulnerable [33]. We know writing about power is sensitive, but we are convinced that this should not be a reason not to do so, especially because of the importance of this concept and its implicit impact. We hope this paper is a genuine contribution to improving EEE.

We see this article as a first reflection on the manifestation of power in EEE. We therefore clearly consider our approach as exploratory. Overall, based on our experiences, we can conclude that there is a strong merit in studying ethics as a potentially disempowered subject in the engineering curriculum. The disempowerment of ethics appears to be the outcome of two main forces, represented by the marketisation of education and the rationalist view on knowledge.

Furthermore, we highlight the importance of several research lines for strengthening our exploratory analysis of power in EEE by the following questions. How do engineers understand social responsibility and whose problems do they focus to solve in their practice? What is the implicit and explicit justification for introducing ethics in the engineering curriculum? How is the role and significance of ethics portrayed to students within their institutions? Is there a gap between the aspirational aspect of what ethics could offer to engineering education and what it actually provides? Is there an ideation gap between how educators teach ethics and how they would prefer to teach the subject? If yes, what is the nature of the constraints affecting educators and what are means to bridge this ideation gap? How can the constraints to engineering ethics education encountered at different levels be reacted to? What changes in public or institutional policy and social practices are needed and what resources and allies can contribute to “empowering” ethics in the engineering curriculum? How can the financial, organisational and ecosystem influences be understood and made more explicit in a way they lead to better engineering ethics education? Further research should prioritize and structure these questions.

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